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Lead Author (Org)	Sara Pittonet Gaiarin (Trust-IT)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Joy Davidson (DCC)
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Versioning and contribution history

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1.0	2023.11.30	Joy Davidson (UEDIN); Sara Pittonet Gaiarin (Trust-IT)	Incorporating comments from PCO and application of further updates on the FIF on the FAIR-IMPACT website

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1. Introduction

To support the adoption and implementation of existing and emerging tools, methods and resources, FAIR-IMPACT has developed the FAIR Implementation Framework (FIF) to help different stakeholders assess their drivers for becoming (more) FAIR-enabling and their current practices so that they can develop realistic action and engagement plans to implement FAIR. A key component of the FIF is a catalogue of resources¹ to share existing FAIR-enabling tools, approaches and solutions that are available to support FAIR Implementation in a practical sense. A beta version of the catalogue was released in May 2023 (M12). An updated version of the catalogue was released on 30 November 2023 (MS2.5) and includes improved browsing functionality. This short report provides an overview of the development of the catalogue of resources and the improved browsing functionality introduced in November 2023.

2. Description of the Milestone

A key aim for the FAIR-IMPACT project is to support the practical implementation of FAIR-enabling practices across three key stakeholder groups: Research Performing Organisations, repositories and data service providers, and national level initiatives. During the first stage of EOSC implementation (2018-2020), a number of projects and initiatives worked to develop metrics for assessing the FAIRness of data and the FAIR-enabling capabilities of organisations and services. Those projects and initiatives have developed a number of tools, approaches and resources to support the implementation of the FAIR principles.

To support the next stage of EOSC Implementation, a new tranche of Horizon Europe funded projects are now working to refine, augment and build on these resources. The availability of such tools and methods is crucial for supporting the practical implementation of the FAIR principles but it can be difficult for different stakeholders to know which to use for specific use cases.

To support the adoption and implementation of existing and emerging tools, methods and resources, **FAIR-IMPACT has developed the FAIR Implementation Framework (FIF)** to help different stakeholders assess their drivers for becoming (more) FAIR-enabling and their current practices so that they can develop realistic action and engagement plans to implement FAIR. The framework illustrates that while the implementation of specific tools and methods is crucial for enabling FAIR, it is equally important to consider other factors that may impact on the overall success of FAIR-enabling efforts. To this end, the FAIR Implementation Framework adapts the approach introduced by the [ACME-FAIR](#) methodology which places an equal emphasis on assessing capabilities for enabling FAIR and on active engagement to ensure uptake of FAIR-enabling practices. The diagram below introduces the seven components of the FIF and provides a set of guiding questions that stakeholders should consider at each stage.

¹ FAIR Implementation Framework Catalogue of Resources <https://catalogue.fair-impact.eu/>

A key component of the FIF is a catalogue of resources to share existing FAIR-enabling tools, approaches and solutions that are available to support FAIR Implementation in a practical sense. The FAIR-IMPACT Implementation team selected more than 60 FAIR-enabling resources developed by initiatives, projects and institutes in Europe. Some of these resources were proposed by providers via an [online form](#) available from the FAIR-IMPACT website. The FI team identified 35 which are suitable to be published in the first complete iteration of the online catalogue.

2.1 About the FAIR Implementation catalogue

The purpose of the FAIR Implementation catalogue is to present a list of resources that will be one component of the FAIR Implementation Framework. The catalogue² is built on Drupal CMS and presents a growing list of resources and enables users to browse the list of tools/solutions by resource type, scientific domain that is targeted, and the intended users for each resource.

35 resources are currently listed, and can be browsed using the following facets:

Scientific domain:

- Agricultural Sciences
- Engineering & Technology
- Humanities

² FAIR Implementation Framework Catalogue of Resources <https://catalogue.fair-impact.eu/>

- Medical & Health Sciences
- Natural Sciences
- Social Sciences
- Domain agnostic

Resource type:

- Guidelines, methodologies and practice documents
- Metadata & ontologies
- Software & tools
- Training materials

Users:

- Data service provider (e.g., repositories, registry services)
- Institutional (e.g., RPOs, Universities)
- International (e.g., pan-European research infrastructures)
- National Repository or Service Manager (e.g., Funding bodies, Government)
- Other

License:

- Open license (e.g., Creative Commons, GNU)
- Restricted license / Order Required

Figure 2 : FAIR Implementation Catalogue - sample view

Each of the resources is presented to users with a title, a short description, information about the resource provider(s), level at which the tool/solution/approach is intended to be used, main users and expertise needed to use it. A direct link to the online reference where the tool/resource is hosted is provided, as well as to the EOSC portal if the resource is published there.

2.1.1 Means of verification

The catalogue is available at the address <https://catalogue.fair-impact.eu/>. The present report will be uploaded on Zenodo.

3. Conclusions and next steps

Over the next weeks the organisations providing the resources will be contacted to cross-check the information provided on the catalogue. Promotion of the catalogue and of the resources will also be done in collaboration with WP7 over the next months, combined with a campaign to collect and make available additional resources.

Periodic updates to the resources included will occur over the life of the project and a final version of the catalogue will be released 31 May 2025.